

EFFICIENT SYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION VIA HIERARCHICAL RESIDUE NUMBER SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>The paper develops a symmetric crypto algorithm based on a hierarchical system of remainder classes that allows to efficiently encrypt text messages using the remainders from dividing the numerical form of the plaintext into the corresponding modules. The peculiarity of this algorithm is its stepwise structure, which allows to gradually reduce the bit depth of modules and operands at each level. The software implementation and relevant experimental studies have shown that the abovementioned algorithm is highly resistant to cryptanalytic attacks due to the multi-level encryption structure and the use of large primes as modules at the first levels. It is established that the cryptographic strength increases with the number of modules, their bit depth, and hierarchical levels. A comparative analysis of the stability of the proposed algorithm and the AES-256 algorithm is carried out. It is determined at which values of the input parameters (bit depth of the modules, number of modules and hierarchy levels) the proposed algorithm demonstrates stability comparable to AES-256, while providing greater flexibility of settings and computational efficiency. The proposed methodology allows changing the number and bit depth of modules, the number of hierarchy levels, and other parameters to achieve the required degree of protection, making the algorithm versatile for different attacks and computing resources. This allows to adaptively adjust the system parameters to achieve the optimal ratio between the level of cryptographic strength and the speed of computation.</p>	<p>symmetric crypto algorithm, hierarchical residue number system, module, remainder, Chinese remainder theorem, coding rules, cryptographic strength, hierarchical levels, bit depth of modules.</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern development of information technologies and globalization of the information space create new challenges for data protection [1, 2]. The number of cyber-attacks is increasing every year [3], aimed at stealing confidential information, financial resources and personal data [4]. In this context, cryptographic methods remain the main tool for ensuring information security [5-7]. Particular attention is drawn to symmetric encryption methods [8] that provide a balance between the speed of data processing and the level of data protection [9, 10].

Existing modern algorithms, such as AES, have demonstrated high efficiency in countering cryptanalytic attacks [11-13]. However, the development of quantum computing [14] and the increase in the computing power of modern systems require the study of new approaches to creating cryptographically secure systems. In this context, the use of the residue number system (RNS) [15, 16] and its forms [17] is a promising direction, as it allows developing algorithms [18, 19] that have high speed and efficiency while maintaining the required level of resistance to attacks [20]. The relevance of the study is determined by the need to strengthen information security in the face of increasing complexity and scale of cyber-attacks. The proposed approach is based on the use of the RNS mathematical apparatus, which combines high encryption efficiency with adaptability to different levels of threats [21-23]. In addition, it is important to find alternatives to traditional cryptographic methods to create new standards for information security in a rapidly changing digital environment. The purpose of this article is to develop a symmetric crypto algorithm based on the use of hierarchical residue number system (HRNS) and to evaluate its stability. The proposed algorithm allows to adaptively adjust the system parameters to achieve an optimal ratio between the level of cryptographic strength and the speed of computation.

II. OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOLUTIONS

In the field of cryptography, there is a constant need to improve algorithms and methods to ensure a high level of security and increase the speed of processing confidential information. One way to enhance the efficiency of cryptographic operations is by using HRNS. Its foundations were laid in [24]. The HRNS proposed by the authors is based on representing large modules as subsystems of residues with smaller modules. This process can be repeated until the modules reach an acceptable length. Calculations can be performed within large dynamic ranges with several small modules, simplifying the transformation of numbers from residue format to positional representation. In [25], a new method for performing base extensions using a hierarchical approach in RNS is proposed. For certain parameters, this significantly reduces calculations. Several studies presented in the article [26] examine the development methods of HRNS and their application in asymmetric cryptography. The authors demonstrate that HRNS can effectively be used for data encryption and signing, providing a large dynamic range and high security level. Additionally, work [27] shows that using specially selected modules of a two-level RNS compared to a conventional one with the same number of modules and the same dynamic range results in hardware savings of 25 to 40% and a complexity reduction of up to 80% in accordance with the RNS. The work [28] indicates the possibility of expanding the dynamic range of the RNS by adding virtual layers, which contributes to the efficient implementation of modular operations for large numbers. This approach can find its application in large cryptographic systems, such as modern RSA encryption algorithms, and underscores the importance of applying a hierarchical approach in RNS for cryptographic tasks. Through it, computational costs can be significantly reduced, and a high level of parallelism can be achieved, which is crucial for the efficiency of cryptographic operations. The paper [29] discusses new symmetric crypto algorithms based on ordinary integer RNS and its modified perfect form. The authors propose two methods. The first involves encrypting by transforming plaintext into a set of residues using corresponding modules (keys) and its subsequent restoration in decimal form using the Chinese remainder theorem (CRT). In the second method, the plaintext is divided into corresponding modules into smaller subblocks, which act as ciphertext. Decryption is performed by searching for residues of the ciphertext using corresponding modules. The authors also conduct research on the cryptographic strength of the proposed crypto algorithms based on the asymptotic distribution law of prime numbers and the use of the Euler function. A logical continuation of this work is the article [30], which develops symmetric encryption algorithms based on RNS. The essence of encryption is that when restoring the decimal representation

of a number from its residues using CRT, multiplication is performed not on found base numbers but on arbitrarily selected, mutually prime with modules, coefficients (keys) of symmetric encryption in RNS, allowing to enhance the cryptographic strength of algorithms. The application of HRNS in cryptography and their research opens new perspectives for creating more efficient and secure cryptographic systems, which can find their implementation in a wide range of information technologies, including confidential information protection, and ensuring information and cyber security.

III. A HIERARCHICAL SYMMETRIC CRYPTOALGORITHM BASED ON A RESIDUE NUMBER SYSTEM

Any decimal number N in the RNS can be given by the set of residues b_i from dividing this number by selected modules p_i, which must be pairwise prime [31]:

$$b_i = N \text{ mod } p_i. \quad (1)$$

The CRT allows to establish a mutually unambiguous correspondence between an integers N in the decimal system

l from the range [0, P), where $P = \prod_{i=1}^l p_i$, $N < P$, and its residues:

$$l \ N \ \prod_{i=1}^l \ bM_i \ [\ _i m_i \ \text{mod } P, \quad (2)$$

P

Where $M_i = \prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^l p_j$, m_i is determined by the expression

$$p_i \ m_i \equiv M_i^{-1} \text{ mod } p_i, \ l \text{ — number of modules.}$$

Another way is to add the product of the previously considered modules sequentially. For example, the module p₁ is added to the residue b₁ until the congruence N₁ mod p₂ = b₂ is satisfied (N₁ = b₁ + α₁p₁, α₁ is the number of additions of the module p₁). Next, the product of the modules p₁p₂ is added to N₁ until the equality N₂ mod p₃ = b₃ (N₂ = N₁ + β₂p₁p₂, β₂ is the number of additions of p₁p₂) is satisfied. At the i-th step (i = 1... l-1), the congruence N_i mod p_{i+1} = b_{i+1} (N_i = N_{i-1} + γ_ip₁p₂p₃...p_i) must be fulfilled. Figure 1 shows the scheme of restoring the decimal representation of a number by its residues based on the addition of the product of modules. It is important to note that when using this approach, the results of intermediate calculations will not go beyond the set range P, which makes it impossible to overflow the bit grid and eliminates the need to perform the operation of finding the remainder modulo P. This method is similar to the Garner algorithm [32], according to which to calculate the coefficients α_i, it is needed to use methods of finding the inverse element by the corresponding module:

$$\alpha_i \equiv \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} b_j \alpha_j \equiv N_i \equiv \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} (p_j \alpha_j) \text{ mod } p_i \equiv \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} 1 \text{ mod } p_i.$$

$$N = \underbrace{b_1 + \alpha_1 p_1}_{\text{mod } p_2} + \underbrace{\alpha_2 p_1 p_2 + \alpha_3 p_1 p_2 p_3 + \dots + \alpha_{i-1} p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_{i-1}}_{\text{mod } p_3}$$

Figure 1. Scheme for restoring the decimal representation of a number by its remainders based on adding the product of modules.

V. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION IN HIERARCHICAL RESIDUE NUMBER SYSTEM

The increase in the volume of information processing, transmission and storage inevitably leads to an increase in the number of modules and their size. This, in turn, causes hardware to become more complex and operations to take longer. Reducing the size of modules and, accordingly, numerical operands allows the HRNS. Let the system of first-level modules p_1, p_2, p_i , arranged in ascending order, provide the possibility of plaintext blocks l N in the range $[0, P)$, where $P \equiv \prod p_i$. The residues b_i are

IV. RULES FOR ENCODING TEXT

To encrypt textual information, it must first be converted into a numerical form. This is usually done using well-known tables of correspondences between letters and numbers (for example, ASCII codes, and letter numbers in the corresponding alphabet). However, when using the decimal system, it is inconvenient when the letter number starts from zero (for example, $a = 00, b = 01$, etc.). Therefore, for transcoding some special characters, the principle is used when the character numbering is represented by a three-digit number starting from 100. This allows to effectively apply the proposed symmetric encryption/decryption method in a stepped RNS. Table 1 shows the character-number correspondence for encoding 167 characters. Obviously, Table 1 can be extended to 900 characters.

Letters of the Ukrainian and English alphabets, numbers, and $i \in \mathbb{1}$ Calculated using formula (1). Next, for each module p_i of the first level, a new system of modules of the second level is selected: $q_{i1}, q_{i2}, \dots, q_{il}$, assuming for simplicity that the number of modules in each system at any level is the same and equal to l . Accordingly, the residues $b_{ij} = b_i \bmod q_{ij}$ are calculated. Then, in turn, the residues of the second level are written in the same way in the system of modules of the third level, subject to the relevant requirements. This procedure continues until the last, k -th level. Thus, each residue of the r -th level corresponds to l systems with l^{r-1} residues. Thus, l^r residues ($l > 1, r = 1, 2, k-1$) are transmitted to

The $r + 1$ level and the ciphertext consists of l^k numbers, which are the residues of the last level of the HRNS. If the number of levels is 1, then the usual symmetric encryption in the RNS takes place. The module sets are known to the sender and the receiver. As a rule, the number of levels is determined by the conditions of a particular task. Such a process of transition to smaller modules greatly simplifies the implementation of an elementary arithmetic device and reduces the time for performing arithmetic operations. Figure 2 shows a diagram of processing residues at the appropriate levels. It should be noted that for cryptography tasks, it is advisable to choose different numbers of modules at different levels. This will significantly increase the complexity of cryptanalysis of such an encryption system, although it will complicate the hardware implementation.

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If the plaintext message converted into numerical form does not satisfy the condition $N < P$, it must be divided into blocks that meet the specified inequality. Decryption in an HRNS is performed in the reverse order. The entire ciphertext is divided into blocks, the number of which is l^k . Then, using one of the methods of recovering a number from its residues, for example, the CRT (2), the residues of a higher level are obtained. At each level of decryption, the number of residues is reduced by a factor of l . At the last level of decryption, the numerical value of the input message is obtained. Figure 3 shows a general scheme of symmetric encryption based on the HRNS.

Figure 3. Scheme of symmetric encryption and decryption based on HRNS

lk residues

Figure 2. Scheme of transfer of residues by levels.

VI. AN EXAMPLE OF A SYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION METHOD IN AN HIERARCHICAL RESIDUE NUMBER SYSTEM

For example, let's take a two-level HRNS with the following sets of modules of the 1st and 2nd levels, respectively: $p_1 = 164359, p_2 = 1287493, p_3 = 1702861; q_{11} = 167, q_{12} = 331, q_{13} = 599, q_{21} = 137, q_{22} = 283, q_{23} = 677, q_{31} = 157, q_{32} = 367, q_{33} = 709$. Suppose that it is needed to encrypt the plaintext “looks cool”, which is divided into two blocks of 5 characters each, including spaces: $S_1 = \text{“looks”}, S_2 = \text{“ cool”}$. According to Table 1, two 15-digit numeric blocks are obtained: $N_1 = 178181181177185, N_2 = 132169181181178$. The results of the hierarchical encryption of blocks N_1 and N_2 are shown in Tables 2-3.

Table 2. Encryption N_1

$N_1 = 178181181177185$	$p_1 = 164359$	$b_1 = 10\ 326$	$q_{11} = 167$	$b_{11} = 139$
			$q_{12} = 331$	$b_{12} = 65$
			$q_{13} = 599$	$b_{13} = 143$
	$p_2 = 1287493$	$b_2 = 1109499$	$q_{21} = 137$	$b_{21} = 73$
			$q_{22} = 283$	$b_{22} = 139$
			$q_{23} = 677$	$b_{23} = 573$
	$p_3 = 1702861$	$b_3 = 1145503$	$q_{31} = 157$	$b_{31} = 31$
			$q_{32} = 367$	$b_{32} = 96$
			$q_{33} = 709$	$b_{33} = 468$

Thus, the blocks $S_1 = \text{“looks”}$ and $S_2 = \text{“ cool”}$ correspond to the residue sets (139, 65, 143, 73, 139, 573, 31, 96, 468) and (63, 133, 264, 37, 251, 403, 37, 260, 656), respectively. The full ciphertext is obtained by concatenating both sets of residues: (139, 65, 143, 73, 139, 573, 31, 96, 468, 63, 133, 264, 37, 251, 403, 37, 260, 656).

Table 3. Encryption N_2

$N_2 = 132169181181178$	$p_1 = 164359$	$b_1 = 136\ 836$	$q_{11} = 167$	$b_{11} = 63$	
			$q_{12} = 331$	$b_{12} = 133$	
			$q_{13} = 599$	$b_{13} = 264$	
	$p_2 = 1287493$	$b_2 = 1\ 074\ 802$	$q_{21} = 137$	$b_{21} = 37$	
			$q_{22} = 283$	$b_{22} = 251$	
			$q_{23} = 677$	$b_{23} = 403$	
				$q_{31} = 157$	$b_{31} = 37$

	$p_3 = 1702861$	$b_3 = 136784$	$q_{32} = 367$	$b_{32} = 260$
			$q_{33} = 709$	$b_{33} = 656$

The decryption process is carried out in reverse order using the CRT, starting from the second level with 9 modules: $q_{11} = 167, q_{12} = 331, q_{13} = 599, q_{21} = 137, q_{22} = 283, q_{23} = 677, q_{31} = 157, q_{32} = 367, q_{33} = 709$. After recovering the residuals of the second level, the decryption is performed using three modules of the first level: $p_1 = 164359, p_2 = 1287493, p_3 = 1702861$. Thus, the ciphertext is divided into two blocks of 9 residues each. The first of them (139, 65, 143, 73, 139, 573, 31, 96, 468) is divided into sub-blocks of three residues, to which the CRT (2) with second-level modules is applied. The resulting three numbers (remainders) are again subjected to the CRT with first-level modules. The procedure is similar

With the second block of the ciphertext. The process and results of decrypting each block are presented in Tables 4 and 5, respectively.

Thus, after combining the decrypted texts of both blocks, the incoming message “looks cool” is obtained.

VII. SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE METHOD

The implementation of the proposed encryption method is based on the Python software. The calculations in the study were performed using HP Pavilion Gaming Laptop 16a0xxx/Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10870H CPU @ 2.20 GHz, 2208 Mhz, 8 Core(s)/32 Gb/1 Tb. At the initial stage, the necessary libraries were exported, a table of encoding letters, numbers and symbols was created, functions for displaying text during encryption and decryption, as well as auxiliary functions for displaying windows on the screen, etc. A description of the main functions of the program implementation and the output of the result of execution on the screen for encryption and decryption is given in Tables 6 and 7, respectively.

Table 6. Description of the main functions of the Encryption software implementation and the result of displaying on the screen

Function description	The result of the screen display
Create and display a job selection window	
Create and display a window for entering text and checking if all characters are in the alphabet	

Table 7. Description of the main functions of the decryption software implementation and the result of displaying on the screen

Table 8 shows the encryption and decryption time for messages of different lengths at each level.

Table 8. Encryption and decryption time for messages of different lengths at each level

Text size, bits	Encryption time,		Decryption time	
	I level	II level	I level	II level
8	7.799943E-06	4.300033E-06	2.659997E-05	1.419999E-05
16	1.279998E-05	7.799943E-06	5.199993E-05	2.020004E-05
32	1.630012E-05	1.369999E-05	4.129997E-05	2.959999E-05
64	2.010015E-05	1.389976E-05	5.489995E-05	4.520011E-05

128	2.790009E-05	2.320018E-05	1.246998E-04	9.370025E-05
256	5.609961E-05	6.760005E-05	6.430999E-04	2.128998E-04
512	1.146998E-04	9.070023E-05	5.221999E-04	4.703999E-04
1024	2.345002E-04	1.778999E-04	7.691999E-04	7.490998E-04
2048	4.413006E-04	3.627992E-04	2.385101E-03	2.479399E-03
4096	9.392999E-04	7.505005E-04	3.148402E-03	3.015401E-03

It is expected that as the message dimension increases from 8 bits to 4096 bits, the time of cryptographic transformations increases by about 100 times. With the same bit depths, the decryption time is longer than the encryption time. This is due to the use of computationally complex CRT operations during decryption. In addition, the time of cryptographic transformations at the second level, which uses smaller modules, is usually less than at the first level.

VIII. EVALUATION OF CRYPTOGRAPHIC STRENGTH OF A CRYPTOGRAPHIC ALGORITHM IN A HIERARCHICAL SYSTEM OF RESIDUAL CLASSES

As noted in [29], the complexity of cryptanalysis of a symmetric encryption method in an integer RNS, provided that the crypto-transformation modules are primes, is

$$O(2^{n-1} \cdot 2^l)$$

where n — bit depth of the modules. When

$$O(2^{n-k} \cdot 2^{l_k})$$

studying the cryptographic resistance of the developed algorithm using the HRNS, it is necessary to take into account the number of levels k and the change in the bit depth of the modules at each level. Therefore, the total time complexity of cryptanalysis at all levels is calculated according to the following formula:

$$O(2^{n-k} \cdot 2^{l_k}) \quad (3)$$

where $n_k = n - k + 1$ — is the bit depth at the k -th level, $l_k = l^k$ is the number of modules at the k -th level.

Taking into account the values of the parameters n_k and l_k , formula (3) will take the following form:

$$O(2^{n-k} \cdot 2^{l^k}) \quad (4)$$

For example, the cryptographic strength of the proposed algorithm for a k -level HRNS with the number of modules on the first level $l = 3$ is described by the expression:

$$O(2^{n-k} \cdot 3^{3^k}) \quad (5)$$

Figure 4 shows a graph that displays the logarithmic dependence of the complexity of cryptanalysis on the number of bits n , the number of modules l , and the levels k . It is clearly observed that with the growth of these parameters,

the complexity of cryptanalysis increases. The results of experimental studies indicate that the stability of the proposed symmetric cryptosystem based on the use of a hierarchical system of residual classes increases with the number of levels and the bit depth of the input parameters (modules).

Figure 4. Dependence of the logarithm of cryptanalysis complexity on the number of bits n, the number of modules l and the levels k.

From the literature review, it is known [33, 34] that the cryptanalysis of the modern symmetric cipher AES-256 is 2^{255} bit operations. From the equality

$$l \cdot k \cdot 2^{n \cdot k \cdot l} = 2^{255}$$

we can find the bits, the

$$k = \frac{255}{l \cdot (n \cdot k \cdot l + 1)}$$

number of levels, and the number of RNS modules that provide the same robustness as the AES-256 algorithm.

After logarithmizing in base 2 and performing elementary arithmetic transformations, we can get

$$k \cdot l^k (n \cdot k \cdot l + 1) = (2 \cdot l^k) \log_2 (n \cdot k \cdot l + 1) = 255. \quad (6)$$

Table 9 shows the values of cryptographic strength for different values of n, l and k.

Table 9. Cryptographic resistance of the developed algorithm in HRNS at different module bit depths, numbers of modules, and levels

n = 8					
k	l = 2	l = 3	l = 4	l = 5	l = 6
1	16	21	26	31	36
2	38.38529	64.34852	98.69703	141.4308	192.5499
3	70.87552	161.7245	322.4294	573.4804	935.368
4	118.3685	383.2921	1012.66	2251.919	4410.793
5	186.3685	873.2921	3064.66	8505.919	19966.79
6	280.1008	1908.024	8863.823	30619.05	85989.95
n = 12					
k	l = 2	l = 3	l = 4	l = 5	l = 6
1	24	32.41504	40.83007	49.24511	57.66015
2	61.08114	107.199	168.398	244.6782	336.0395
3	121.1496	294.1508	602.4385	1086.081	1785.147
4	220.7706	772.7267	2101.278	4736.218	9347.264

5	386.7706	1993.727	7227.278	20367.22	48233.26
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Table 9 demonstrates that the proposed symmetric cryptographic algorithm based on the HRNS provides a level of cryptographic strength comparable to the AES-256 algorithm at certain values of the parameters n , l , and k . In particular, for 8-bit modules with $l = 2$, 6 levels are required to exceed the AES-256 strength. Increasing the number of modules leads to a decrease in encryption levels (if $l = 3$, then $k = 4$; if $l = 4-6$, then $k = 3$). For 12-bit modules with $l = 2$, the strength of the proposed cryptalgorithm exceeds the strength of AES-256 at the fifth level. With an increase in the number of modules ($l = 3-5$), the condition of exceeding the AES-256 strength is fulfilled at the third level, and at $l = 6$ – at the second level. Thus, varying the bit depth of the modules, their number, and hierarchy levels allows us to achieve the appropriate cryptographic strength of the proposed algorithm depending on the specific task.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

For the first time, a symmetric cryptalgorithm based on the HRNS has been proposed that allows to efficiently convert text messages into numerical form and ensure their encryption using the remaining modules. A feature of the algorithm is its stepwise structure, which makes it possible to consistently reduce the bit depth of the modules at each level and ensure the preservation of the original information. Experimental studies have demonstrated that the proposed algorithm is highly resistant to attacks due to the use of large prime numbers in the system of modules and a multi-level encryption structure. It is established that cryptographic resistance increases with the number of modules, their bit depth, and hierarchy levels. A comparative analysis of the stability of the proposed algorithm and the AES-256 algorithm is carried out. It is indicated at what values of the input parameters (bit depth of the modules, number of modules, and hierarchy levels) the algorithm based on the RNS demonstrates stability comparable to AES-256, while providing greater flexibility of settings and computational efficiency. The proposed methodology allows changing the bit depth of the modules, the number of hierarchy levels, and other parameters to achieve the required level of protection. This makes the algorithm universal for use in conditions of different levels of threats and computer system resources. In general, the conducted studies confirm the effectiveness and prospects of using a symmetric cryptographic algorithm based on the HRNS to ensure the protection of information in the modern digital environment. The proposed approach opens up new opportunities for the development of cryptography that meet the challenges of the digital age.

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